

Podium Presentation Session 7, Friday 15:30-15:50

Neoplastic diseases and human evolution: new insights into its evolutionary history through a palaeopathological assessment of a 1.6 Ma robust australopithecine from East Turkana, Kenya

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Current research has evidenced that the antiquity of neoplastic diseases among hominins dates as far as 1.9 million years ago [1-2]. In addition, anecdotic scattered case-studies, theoretical approaches, and side identifications have proven that oncological conditions were a reality throughout the evolution of our lineage [3]. Although there is robust evidence to support this, the role of neoplasia in the context of hominin adaptation remains relatively unexplored.

Here we present evidence of neoplastic lesions from the African Pleistocene hominin record and discuss the methodological and theoretical challenges of studying this complex genetic condition. Key case-studies are presented, including the analysis of KNM-ER-406, a 1.6 Ma robust australopithecine skull discovered by Richard Leakey in 1969 in East Turkana, Kenya (Africa) [4]. We have conducted a macro- and micro-oscopic assessment of a lesion present in the frontal bone of this specimen, which we interpret as a tumour (possibly a dermoid/epidermoid cyst, Differential Diagnosis: Osteoid Osteoma, Osteoblastoma), representing one of the oldest evidence of neoplastic conditions in human evolution. Its malignancy or benignancy is discussed through a differential diagnosis, and we further explore how a hunter-gatherer lifestyle is linked to epidemiological causes of neoplastic diseases, including malignancy. The case of KNM-ER 406 is compared to others from South Africa (i.e., *Paranthropus robustus*, SK 7923 1.8-1.6 Ma and *Australopithecus sediba* U.W. 88-37 1.7 Ma), and its evolutionary significance is considered given the anatomical location of the lesion.

The incidence of neoplastic diseases in early prehistory is a debated issue among the field of palaeopathology, with cancer commonly considered as a rare condition. The present contribution suggests that neoplasia, including malignancy, may have been a much more common disease in the past, potentially playing an important role in our evolutionary history.

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References: [1] Randolph-Quinney, P. S., Williams, S. A., Steyn, M., Meyer, M. R., Smilg, J. S., Churchill, S. E., Augustine, T., Tafforeau, P., Berger, L. R., 2016. Osteogenic tumour in *Australopithecus sediba*: Earliest hominin evidence for neoplastic disease. *South African Journal of Science* 112(7-8), 1-7. [2] Odes, E. J., Randolph-Quinney, P. S., Steyn, M., Throckmorton, Z., Smilg, J. S., Zipfel, B., Augustine, T., Beer, F., Hoffman, J., Franklin, R., Berger, L. R., 2016. Earliest hominin cancer: 1.7-million-year-old osteosarcoma from Swartkrans Cave, South Africa. *South African Journal of Science* 112(7-8), 1-5. [3] Capasso, L. L. Antiquity of cancer. *International Journal of Cancer* 113, 2-13 (2005). [4] Leakey, R. E. F., Mungai, J. M., Walker, A. C., 1972. New australopithecines from East Rudolf, Kenya (II). *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 36(2), 235-251.